

BEHAVIOUR OF RATIONAL PRIMES IN THE RING OF ALGEBRAIC INTEGERS

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Abstract:

We know that the primes in \mathbb{Z} (hereafter referred as rational primes) are irreducible in \mathbb{Z} i.e they don't have proper factorization. If R is any factorization domain such that \mathbb{Z} is properly contained in R then are these rational primes also irreducible in R ? The answer to this question in general is No. For example, 13 is prime in \mathbb{Z} but 13 is not prime in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$ as we can write 13 as: $13 = (2 + 3i)(2 - 3i)$ where both $2 + 3i$ & $2 - 3i$ are irreducible (rather non units) in $\mathbb{Z}[i]$. In this paper we will see how the rational primes split in the ring of algebraic integers.

Key Words: Algebraic Number Field, Norm, Integral Basis, Discriminant & Ramify

1. Introduction:

An Algebraic number field is a subfield of \mathbb{C} (field of complex numbers) of the form $Q(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$, where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ are algebraic numbers. Let K be an algebraic number field. A basis for O_K is called an integral basis for K . Let $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be an integral basis for K . Then $D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$ is called the discriminant of K and is denoted by $d(K)$ or d_K . Moreover, in any algebraic number field K , every proper integral ideal of O_K can be expressed uniquely up to order as a product of prime ideals. Let p be a rational prime. Suppose $\langle p \rangle$ factors in O_K as $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_g^{e_g}$, where P_1, P_2, \dots, P_g are distinct prime ideals of O_K lying above p where, $e_i = e_K(P_i)$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, g$. If $e_i > 1$ for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, g\}$ then p is said to be ramify in K .

Definition 1.1: (Basis of an Ideal)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let I be a nonzero ideal of O_K . If $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is a set of elements of I such that every element $\beta \in I$ can be expressed uniquely in the form as $\beta = x_1\alpha_1 + x_2\alpha_2 + \dots + x_n\alpha_n$ where $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{Z}$ then $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is called a basis for the ideal I .

Definition 1.2: (Discriminant of n Elements in an Algebraic Number Field of Degree n)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ be n elements of the field K . Let σ_k ; $1 \leq k \leq n$ denote the n distinct monomorphisms from K to \mathbb{C} . For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ let $\alpha_i^{(1)} = \sigma_1(\alpha_i) = \alpha_i$, $\alpha_i^{(2)} = \sigma_2(\alpha_i)$, \dots , $\alpha_i^{(n)} = \sigma_n(\alpha_i)$ denote the conjugate of α_i relative to K . Then the discriminant of $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ is

$$D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) = \left(\det \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1^{(1)} & \dots & \alpha_n^{(1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \alpha_1^{(n)} & \dots & \alpha_n^{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \right)^2$$

Definition 1.3: (Discriminant of an Ideal)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let I be a nonzero ideal of O_K . Let $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be a basis of I . Then the discriminant $D(I)$ of the ideal I is the nonzero integer given by $D(I) = D(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$.

Definition 1.4: (Index of θ)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let $\theta \in K$ be such that $K = Q(\theta)$. Then the index of θ , denoted by $\text{ind}(\theta)$ is the positive integer given by $D(\theta) = D(1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^{n-1}) = (\text{ind}(\theta))^2 d(K)$. Note that if $D(\theta)$ is square free then $\text{ind}(\theta) = 1$ and $D(\theta) = d(K)$. Thus $\{1, \theta, \theta^2, \dots, \theta^{n-1}\}$ is an integral basis for K .

Definition 1.5: (Conjugates of θ over Q)

Let $\theta \in \mathbb{C}$ be any algebraic number i.e θ is a root of some monic irreducible polynomial $p(x)$ of least degree over Q then the roots of $p(x)$ are called the conjugates of θ over Q .

Definition 1.6: (Norm of an element θ over Q)

It is defined as product of all conjugates of θ over Q . It is denoted by $N_{K/Q}(\theta)$.

Definition 1.7: (Norm of an integral ideal)

Let K be an algebraic number field of degree n . Let I be a nonzero ideal of O_K . Then the norm of the ideal I denoted by $N(I)$, is the positive integer defined by $N(I) = \sqrt{\frac{D(I)}{d(K)}}$

2. Main Section:

Let θ be a root of $x^5 - 5 = 0$.

Let $f(x) = x^5 - 5$, is monic and irreducible over \mathbb{Z} . $[K:Q] = 5 = n$

Then Discriminant of θ is given by: $D(\theta) = (-1)^{n(n-1)/2} N(f'(\theta))$

$D(\theta) = N(5\theta^4) = N(5) N(\theta^4) = N(5) (N(\theta))^4 = 5^5 5^4 = 5^9$

By definition of Index of θ , possible values of $\text{ind}(\theta)$ are 1, 5, 5^2 , 5^3 , 5^4

Theorem 2.1:

Let $K = \mathbb{Q}(\theta)$ be an algebraic number field of degree $n \geq 2$, where θ is an algebraic integer. If the minimal polynomial of θ satisfies Eisenstein Criteria for a rational prime p , then p does not divide the index of θ .

Since $x^5 - 5$ being the minimal polynomial of θ satisfies Eisenstein Criteria for $p = 5$, so 5 doesn't divide the $\text{ind}(\theta)$. Thus only possible value of $\text{ind}(\theta)$ is 1. Hence $D(\theta) = d(K)$.

Therefore $\{1, \theta, \theta^2, \theta^3, \theta^4\}$ is an integral basis of K .

Theorem 2.2:

Let K be an algebraic number field with $[K:\mathbb{Q}] = n$. Let p be a rational prime. Suppose $\langle p \rangle$ factors in O_K as $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_g^{e_g}$, where P_1, P_2, \dots, P_g are distinct prime ideals of O_K . Suppose that f_i is the inertial degree of P_i in K . Then, $e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + \dots + e_g f_g = n$,

Note that $g \leq n$

In present case, $g \leq 5$

If $g = 5: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3 + e_4 f_4 + e_5 f_5 = 5$

i.e. $e_1 = f_1 = e_2 = f_2 = e_3 = f_3 = e_4 = f_4 = e_5 = f_5 = 1$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5$; $N(P_i) = p$

If $g = 4: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3 + e_4 f_4 = 5$

Wlog, assume that $e_1 f_1 = 2$ and $e_2 f_2 = e_3 f_3 = e_4 f_4 = 1$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$ and $e_2 = f_2 = e_3 = f_3 = e_4 = f_4 = 1$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4$; $N(P_1) = p^2, N(P_2) = N(P_3) = N(P_4) = p$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2 P_3 P_4$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = N(P_3) = N(P_4) = p$

If $g = 3: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3 = 5$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$ and $(e_2, f_2) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$ and $(e_3, f_3) = (1, 1)$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = p^2 = N(P_2), N(P_3) = p$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2^2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = p^2, N(P_2) = p = N(P_3)$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = p = N(P_3), N(P_2) = p^2$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^2 P_2^2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = N(P_3) = p$

Wlog, assume that $e_1 f_1 = 3$ and $(e_2, f_2) = (e_3, f_3) = (1, 1)$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 3), (3, 1)$ and $e_2 = f_2 = e_3 = f_3 = 1$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = p^3, N(P_2) = N(P_3) = p$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^3 P_2 P_3$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = N(P_3) = p$

If $g = 2: e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 = 5$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 4), (4, 1)$ and $e_2 = f_2 = 1$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p^4, N(P_2) = p$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^4 P_2$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = p$

Wlog, assume that $e_1 f_1 = 3$ and $e_2 f_2 = 2$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 3), (3, 1)$ and $(e_2, f_2) = (1, 2), (2, 1)$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p^3, N(P_2) = p^2$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1 P_2^2$; $N(P_1) = p^3, N(P_2) = p$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^3 P_2$; $N(P_1) = p, N(P_2) = p^2$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^3 P_2^2$; $N(P_1) = N(P_2) = p$

If $g = 1: e_1 f_1 = 5$

$(e_1, f_1) = (1, 5), (5, 1)$

Thus, $\langle p \rangle = P_1$; $N(P_1) = p^5$

Or

$\langle p \rangle = P_1^5$; $N(P_1) = p$

Let us see how rational primes split in O_K

Theorem 2.3:

Let $K = \mathbb{Q}(\theta)$ be an algebraic number field of degree n such that $O_K = \mathbb{Z}[\theta]$. Let p be a rational prime, let $f(x) = \text{irr}_{\mathbb{Q}} \theta \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$. Let $\bar{\cdot}$ denote the natural map: $\mathbb{Z}[x] \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p[x]$ where $\mathbb{Z}_p = \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$. Let $\bar{f}(x) = g_1^{e_1}(x) g_2^{e_2}(x) \dots$

$g_r^{e_r}(x)$ where $g_i(x)$ are distinct monic irreducibles in $Z_p[x]$, $1 \leq i \leq r$ and e_1, e_2, \dots, e_r are positive integers. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, let $f_i(x)$ be any monic polynomial of $Z[x]$ such that $\bar{f}_i = g_i$. Set $P_i = \langle p, f_i(\theta) \rangle$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Then P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r are distinct prime ideals of O_K with $\langle p \rangle = P_1^{e_1} P_2^{e_2} \dots P_r^{e_r}$ and $N(P_i) = p^{\deg f_i}$; $1 \leq i \leq r$.

For $p = 2$

$$x^5 - 5 = (x - 1)(x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1) \text{ over } Z_2[x] \text{ and } x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + x + 1 \text{ is irreducible over } Z_2$$

$$\text{Set } P_1 = \langle 2, \theta - 1 \rangle; N(P_1) = 2$$

$$\text{Set } P_2 = \langle 2, \theta^4 + \theta^3 + \theta^2 + \theta + 1 \rangle; N(P_2) = 2^4 = 16$$

$$\text{Thus } \langle 2 \rangle = P_1 P_2$$

For $p = 3$

$$x^5 - 5 = (x - 2)(x^4 + 2x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 1) \text{ over } Z_3[x] \text{ and } x^4 + 2x^3 + x^2 + 2x + 1 \text{ is irreducible over } Z_3$$

$$\text{Set } P_1 = \langle 3, \theta - 2 \rangle; N(P_1) = 3$$

$$\text{Set } P_2 = \langle 3, \theta^4 + 2\theta^3 + \theta^2 + 2\theta + 1 \rangle; N(P_2) = 3^4 = 81$$

$$\text{Thus, } \langle 3 \rangle = P_1 P_2$$

Theorem 2.4:

Let K be an algebraic number field. Then the rational prime ramifies in K iff p divides d_K . As $d_K = 5^9$ and $p = 5$, which is a rational prime divides d_K , i.e. $p = 5$ ramifies in O_K

For $p = 5$

$$x^5 - 5 = x^5 \text{ over } Z_5[x]$$

$$\text{Set } P = \langle 5, \theta \rangle; N(P) = 5$$

$$\text{Thus } \langle 5 \rangle = P^5$$

3. References:

1. Saban Alaca and Kenneth S. Williams, Introductory Algebraic Number Theory, Cambridge University Press.